

EXPLORING THE THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF KALIUM MURIATICUM IN ALLEVIATING THE SYMPTOMS OF ALLERGIC RHINITIS BY ASSESSING ABSOLUTE EOSINOPHILIC COUNT. A PROSPECTIVE CLINICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background- Allergic rhinitis affects a significant global population, particularly teenagers, and has considerable effects on quality of life. The current research presents a proposal to examine the efficacy of Kalium muriaticum in treating allergic rhinitis by evaluating its impact on absolute eosinophil count. Despite limited research on Kalium muriaticum for this condition, the study aims to determine its potential as a therapy for reducing allergic rhinitis symptoms. Overall, this investigation could contribute valuable insights into expanding treatment options for allergic rhinitis.

Material and Method- The outpatient clinic of Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) was the site of a prospective clinical study. 60 patients between the ages of 18 and 45 were evaluated for inclusion and exclusion. Thirty people with allergic rhinitis had their absolute eosinophil count measured before and after the intervention.

Result- Significant subjective and objective improvement were seen in individuals treated with Kalium muriaticum, according to the research. There was a larger frequency among men, as shown by the fact that 56.6% of the participants were male. Patients in the 25–30 age group had the greatest prevalence of allergic rhinitis (60.00%). A substantial decline from 91.96 to 13.14 was seen in the mean Absolute Eosinophilic Count after the intervention. A determined t-value of 10.18 was used in the paired t-test, which yielded a significant result ($p < 0.00$).

Conclusion- An often-overlooked part of homeopaths' everyday practice, the research highlighted the possibility of Kalium muriaticum as addressing allergenic rhinitis. The remedy's quick action, short symptom-resolution time, and decreased absolute eosinophilic count are all seen here.

Key Words- Homeopathy, Hay fever, Allergic Rhinitis, Absolute Erythrocyte Count, Kalium Muriaticum.

1. Introduction

An allergic pandemic has developed because of a sharp rise in the prevalence of allergy-related rhinitis before its first report in 1870. Allergy Rhinitis are characterized by aberrant immunological responses, although the exact processes causing these reactions are still unclear [1]. Immunoglobulin E (IgE) has been the key player since its discovery in the late 60s. The mechanism has been well studied and inferred. IgE has been known to be a controlling factor of asthma, an allergic reaction to atopic dermatitis especially food allergies [2]. Recent data that disclose the complicated relationship between conditions in the environment that causes, communicate and predispose to allergy diseases has been progressed. Among these causes, there are predisposition at birth, impaired epithelial barrier function, impaired immunological tolerance, environment-related variables, changes in food and microbiota, and changes in the environment [3]. Watery nasal discharge, itchiness, sneezes, and congestion are the symptoms of allergic rhinitis, a condition that stimulates the body's response against the nasal salivary glands [4]. Intriguingly, inspect data and estimates that, thirty to twenty percent of Indians suffer from nasal allergies while fourteen percent of those who have them, ultimately develop bronchial asthma. Allergic Rhinitis adversely affect the quality of life and productivity of patient, experiencing symptoms such as disrupted sleep, exhaustion, mood changes, and reduced cognitive functioning [5]. An analysis has been made comparing the incidence, epidemiology and economic impact of allergic rhinitis in the

United States and in India, India's communities with this type of disease not only have difficulty of breathing but also has reduced standard quality of living by 46% and 38% respectively [6].

Natural or therapeutic relief is possible for symptoms including rhinorrhoea, nasal swollen and nasal blockage, and sneezing that are associated with allergic rhinitis, as per the recommendations made by ARIA (Allergic Sneezing and its Impact on Asthma). That further categorize patients as moderate, severe, or mild in nature based on whether their symptoms are intermittent or persistent [7, 8].

To estimate the level of peripheral and absolute eosinophil count, total blood count is assessed, and a nasal smear is analysed for the presence of eosinophils. Despite its rarity, IgE plays a vital role in the development of allergies. Atopic individuals may have levels that are over a thousand times higher than normal, even though it only makes up 0.05% of total immunoglobulins. In a peripheral smear, the usual range for eosinophils is 0% to 6%, with an absolute eosinophilic count 40-440 cells per cubic mm [9,10,11].

1.1 Need for Study

People in today's fast-paced environment often choose for faster methods of recovery, which include suppressing or palliating symptoms, rather than waiting for their diseases to cure natural way of disappearance of symptoms. The efficacy of current treatments for allergic rhinitis, such as antibiotics, immunotherapy, and anti-histaminic drugs like Montelukast and Levocetirizine, is declining.

Although conventional therapy is effective in reducing symptoms, it is not effective in controlling recurrences [12,13].

Recurrences may be prevented and quality of life can be improved with homoeopathic intervention. Homoeopathic medicines may improve the constitution, address current symptoms, reduce infection risk, and ease suppressions of the past. This research aimed to examine the therapeutic value of Kalium Muriaticum in alleviating the sufferings of Allergic Rhinitis by measuring the reduction in the absolute eosinophil count [6].

1.2 Aims and Objective of Study

Aim- To ascertain the efficacy of Kalium Muriaticum in Allergic Rhinitis by assessing absolute eosinophil count.

Objectives-

- In order to compare the pre- and post-treatment values of the absolute eosinophil count.
- For the purpose of determining if Kalium muriaticum is useful in the treatment of allergic rhinitis.

2. Materials and Methods

Study Type- Interventional Study

Study Design- An experimental, non-randomised, prospective, before-and-after comparative research. The study protocol was approved by the IEC (Institutional Ethical Committee) and followed GCP (Good Clinical Practice) principles.

Study Setting- Only 32 of the 60 individuals that were screened were originally enrolled. With two cases removed due to withdrawal, the final analysis included 30 patients who met the study's inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria-

- pre-diagnosed and newly diagnosed case of Allergic Rhinitis with sneezing, nasal pruritis and congestion, eye redness, puffiness, and watery discharge, without any complications are to be taken for the study.
- Both male and female of age between 18-45 are included.

Exclusion Criteria-

- Patients exhibiting overt pathology, including asthma, chronic sinusitis, otitis media, etc.
- Pregnant and lactating mothers

Intervention- Case taking and administration of Kalium Muriaticum 30C/200C

Outcome Assessment- The study involved 30 patients, ranging in age from 18 to 45, who were given Kalium Muriaticum after a clinical diagnosis of Allergic Rhinitis. In order to determine if there was an improvement, the Absolute Eosinophil Count was measured both before and after the intervention.

Statistical Analysis- To evaluate the efficacy of Kalium Muriaticum, a paired t test was used to compare the Absolute Eosinophilic count values before and after the intervention. Software such as SPSS, Power Bi has been used for the evaluation the data.

3. Result and Observation-

Initially, 32 out of 60 patients that screened were recruited. With 2 instances removed due to withdrawal, the final analysis includes 30 patients. The majority of Rhinitis patients (60.00%) were found to be between the ages of 25 and 30, followed by 19–24 (33.33%), 31–36 (3.33%), and 37–42 (3.33%). Men had a greater prevalence of the condition than females, with 43.33% of females and 56.67% of men affected with Allergic Rhinitis, according to the research. As far as the study's subjects are concerned, dust is the most common allergen, accounting for 40% of cases. Next on the list are weather changes (at 26.67%), family history (20.00%), pet allergies (10.00%), and food (3.33%). 56.67% of the individuals in the study had a positive family history of allergies.

Table1: Distribution of patients according to age

Patients Distribution Age Wise		
Age Category	Number of Patients	Percentage
19-24	10	33.33%
25-30	18	60.00%
31-36	1	3.33%
37-42	1	3.33%
Total	30	100.00%

Distribution of Patients Age Wise(N=30)

Figure1: Pie diagram representing Age-wise distribution of patients

Table2: Distribution of Patients according to Gender

Distribution of Patients Gender		
Gender	Number of Patients	Percentage
Female	13	43.33%
Male	17	56.67%
Total	30	100%

Distribution of Patients Gender Wise(N=30)

Figure2: Gender wise distribution of patient.

Table 3- Distribution of patient according to Exposure/Risk factor
Patients Distribution with Exposure/Risk Factor

Exposure/Risk Factor	Count	% Distribution
DUST	12	40.00%
FAMILY HISTORY	6	20.00%
FOOD	1	3.33%
PET	3	10.00%
WEATHER CHANGE	8	26.67%
Total	30	100.00%

Patients Distribution by Exposure/Risk Factor

Fig- 3 Exposure/Risk factor distribution associated in condition of Allergic Rhinitis.
Table 4 Paired t-test and Descriptive statistics of the Absolute Eosinophil Count before and after the intervention.

Absolute Eosinophil Count	N	Mean±SD	Min	Max	T Statistic Value	P-Value
before	30	597.93 ± 91.96			10.18	0.001**
intervention			504	865		
after	30	338.46 ± 13.14	145	560		
Mean difference		259.47± 13.14				

Patients Wise Condition Pre & Post Treatment

Fig -4- Graph representing changes in Absolute Eosinophil count pre and post treatment.
The Absolute Eosinophilic Count decreases after homoeopathic intervention with Kalium Muriaticum, 99

as seen in Table 4 and figures 4 . Two patients out of thirty had a rise in count, two showed no change, and the other twenty-six had a decrease. Environmental factors or sustaining reasons might be responsible for the increase in count for 2 patients.

The estimated t score of 10.18 from the pair-t test has shown a substantial decrease in the average mean of $-597.93 + 91.96$ to $338.46 + 13.14$, and the result was significant ($p < 0.00$). The improvement in Overall Eosinophilic Count supports the conclusion that Kalium muriaticum is effective in the management of allergic rhinitis.

4. Discussion-

Due to increased sensitivity to environmental allergens, Allergic Rhinitis (AR) is quickly becoming a major health problem in today's fast-paced society [6]. Domestic carpets, mattresses, beds, pillows, pillowcases, and garments are ideal habitats for house-dust mites, according to US research that backed up these worries (reference check). This aligns with my own observations.

In allergic rhinitis (AR), an IgE-mediated immune responses affects the upper airway mucosa, leading to symptoms as watery eyes, paroxysmal sneezing, itching, nasal congestion, and rhinorrhoea [7]. Based on how often symptoms occur, AR is categorized as either Persistent AR or Intermittent AR according to ARIA standards [14].

Allergic rhinitis headed through two phases: early and late. The first reaction is distinguished by vascular leakage, vasodilation, and glandular secretion caused by Mast cell and IgE (Immunoglobulin E) antibodies. This response is tailed by infiltration of neutrophils and eosinophils [15]. In reactions involving type 1 hypersensitivity, eosinophils are crucial. Proteolytic enzymes and protein molecules released by eosinophils, such as the eosinophil cationic polypeptide and the main basic protein, may be detected using a variety of techniques [16].

This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of Kalium Muriaticum in reducing Allergic Rhinitis symptoms by looking at the drop in Absolute Eosinophil Count. Of the 30 cases included in the analysis, 17 were male (56.67%) and 13 were female (43.33%), which is in line with earlier findings that show a higher prevalence of allergic rhinitis in men [17]. Consistent with other research showing a peak incidence in this age range [18], the greatest incidence of the allergic rhinitis was seen in the age of 25–30 year. Consistent with other findings that point to a hereditary susceptibility to allergic rhinitis, 56.67 percent of patients showed a positive family history [18].

The Absolute Eosinophil Count decreased significantly after Kalium Muriaticum was administered. This was accompanied by an improvement in allergy symptoms. The mean SD dropped from $597.93 + 91.96$ before treatments to $338.46 + 13.14$ after the intervention. Absolute Eosinophilic Count values range from 145/cubic mm to 865/cubic mm, shows a significant decrease from the highest range before treatment. Therefore, it signifies that Kalium muriaticum can be thought of as an alternative to the most prescribed medicines for Allergic Rhinitis, and it is very efficient in treating the condition.

5. Conclusion-

The present study highlights the therapeutic potential of Kalium muriaticum as a therapy for allergic rhinitis. A substantial alleviation of symptoms was seen after the intervention, as determined by monitoring the reduction in Absolute Eosinophil Count of thirty patients. Kalium muriaticum proved as a significantly efficient treatment for allergic rhinitis, according to the results, that aligns with the decrease in the count of Absolute Eosinophilic Count. Furthermore, the study adds to the increasing amount of data that supports the use of alternative treatments for this condition. To confirm these results and investigate the broader therapeutic use of Kalium muriaticum, more research and clinical studies are required.

6. Conflict of Interest- None Found

7. References-

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